

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 6 Results of (U-Th)/He dating.

sample 7-v15-9															
z7-v15-9-107	zircon	349.2	27.94	155.2	74.1	7.0	172.3	0.48	238.7	2.68	0.72	40.77		832.0	17.0
z7-v15-9-128	zircon	230.5	18.44	112.4	153.2	2.8	147.7	1.36	134.1	3.33	0.72	41.83		434.4	7.8
z7-v15-9-2	zircon	243.8	19.50	245.9	103.9	2.1	269.9	0.42	315.4	31.15	0.87	93.77		1828	16
z7-v15-9-20	zircon	239.7	19.2	297.7	161.6	0.0	334.9	0.54	321.7	3.9	0.73	43.1		312.5	5.1
z7-v15-9-3	zircon	234.4	18.75	214.7	129.5	1.6	244.5	0.60	240.1	5.88	0.76	49.72		454.3	7
z7-v15-9-34	zircon	205.7	16.5	70.2	15.0	0.3	73.6	0.21	64.4	6.3	0.78	51.9		686	16
z7-v15-9-35	zircon	263.9	21.1	30.0	13.4	0.1	33.1	0.45	38.9	9.9	0.81	62.9		2996	57
z7-v15-9-43	zircon	218.4	17.5	244.9	111.5	0.4	270.6	0.46	253.6	6.9	0.78	54.2		461	11
z7-v15-9-46	zircon	219.9	17.59	96.7	71.7	1.4	113.2	0.74	112.7	13.25	0.82	68.60		376	7.4
z7-v15-9-52	zircon	271.0	21.68	83.5	43.4	1.4	93.5	0.52	115.9	13.81	0.83	70.82		977	11
z7-v15-9-55	zircon	199.3	15.94	113.7	30.8	1.4	120.8	0.27	103.1	6.86	0.78	53.56		1018	40
z7-v15-9-84	zircon	287.5	23.00	158.7	57.3	4.8	171.9	0.36	219.0	9.74	0.80	60.16		404	13
z7-v15-9-92	zircon	253.3	20.27	241.8	73.9	1.3	258.8	0.31	296.3	14.10	0.82	66.44		347.9	6

Detrital zircons from pebbels composed of Cambrian metasediments												
Grain#	mineral	Age, Ma	err., Ma	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	147Sm (ppm)	[U]e	Th/U	He (nmol/g)	mass (ug)	Ft	ESR
sample 15-v15-28												
z15_v15_28_3-1	zircon	229.1	18.3	115.2	62.8	0.1	129.6	0.55	124.9	5.1	0.77	50.5
z15_v15_28_3-3	zircon	277.7	22.2	375.2	161.2	0.7	412.3	0.43	468.6	4.2	0.74	45.3
z15_v15_28_3-4	zircon	242.5	19.4	134.1	109.6	0.5	159.3	0.82	169.0	7.8	0.80	58.6
z15_v15_28_3-5	zircon	236.3	18.9	69.2	19.2	0.3	73.6	0.28	77.8	10.2	0.81	63.7
z15_v15_28_3-6	zircon	261.3	20.9	258.4	52.8	0.2	270.6	0.20	326.7	15.4	0.84	73.3
sample 15-v15-25												
z15_v15_25_1-1	zircon	178.4	14.3	316.1	269.7	3.4	378.2	0.85	370.7	4.7	1.00	50.0
z15_v15_25_1-2	zircon	225.6	18.0	86.4	81.4	1.0	105.1	0.94	105.8	10.8	0.81	64.3
z15_v15_25_1-3	zircon	193.3	15.5	148.8	183.3	1.5	191.0	1.23	152.7	5.3	0.75	48.7
z15_v15_25_1-5	zircon	213.2	17.1	173.0	77.6	0.6	190.8	0.45	170.2	4.8	0.76	49.5
z15_v15_25_1-6	zircon	222.2	17.8	155.8	106.0	0.8	180.2	0.68	168.3	6.0	0.77	50.5
z15_v15_25_1-7	zircon	240.3	19.2	101.8	129.3	0.8	131.6	1.27	135.2	6.8	0.78	54.1